

A STUDY ON JOB SATISFACTION AMONG THE EMPLOYEES OF KAUVERY HOSPITAL, ALWARPET, CHENNAI

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Abstract:

This research investigates job satisfaction among employees at Kauvery Hospital, Alwarpet, Chennai, through a descriptive and comparative study. The primary objective is to assess job satisfaction among hospital employees. The study sample consists of 110 participants, and the research employs percentage analysis, correlation, and chi-square methods. Data was collected using a structured questionnaire and analyzed with SPSS software. The study provides an overview of the organization's profile and delves into conceptual background, percentage analysis, correlation, and chi-square results. The findings, suggestions, and conclusions drawn from the research aim to contribute to the understanding of job satisfaction among hospital employees. The study's results can inform strategies to enhance employee satisfaction, ultimately improving healthcare services. The research provides valuable insights for healthcare organizations, policymakers, and future researchers in this field.

Key Words: Hospital Employees, Healthcare Employees, Job Satisfaction, Job, Work Environment.

Introduction:

Job satisfaction is a crucial aspect of employee well-being and performance in the healthcare industry, where high levels of stress and burnout are common. Hospitals, in particular, rely on a dedicated and motivated workforce to provide quality patient care and ensure positive health outcomes. However, low job satisfaction among hospital employees can lead to decreased productivity, increased turnover, and compromised patient care. This study examines job satisfaction among healthcare workers, identifying influential factors and providing recommendations for improvement. It aims to determine what affects job satisfaction, measure current satisfaction levels, understand the impact on performance and patient care, and suggest enhancements for healthcare organizations. Key factors influencing job satisfaction include work environment, compensation and benefits, work-life balance, career growth opportunities, leadership quality, and workload. The study involves reviewing existing research, conducting surveys, interviewing staff, analysing data, and compiling findings into actionable recommendations. Improving job satisfaction is crucial for better employee retention and patient care, and addressing these factors can significantly enhance the work environment and overall performance. Healthcare organizations should prioritize improving work conditions, compensation, work-life balance, career development opportunities, and leadership quality. Additionally, they should promote professionalism, enthusiasm, resourcefulness, self-directedness, ethics, unselfishness, and strategic-mindedness. Employee satisfaction is influenced by organizational variables such as overall individual satisfaction, compensation and benefits, nature of work, work environment and conditions, job content, opportunities for promotion, and safety measures, as well as personal variables like personality, age, education, and learning. By addressing these factors, healthcare organizations can create a positive and productive work environment, leading to long-term success and improved healthcare outcomes.

Statement of Problem:

The healthcare industry is critical for the well-being of society, providing essential medical services and care. However, it faces numerous challenges that can impact the job satisfaction of its employees. Job satisfaction among healthcare professionals is a significant factor influencing their performance, retention, and the overall quality of care provided to patients. Despite the critical role of healthcare workers, there is a growing concern about their job satisfaction levels due to factors such as high work demands, long hours, emotional stress, and administrative burdens. Employee job satisfaction is a critical component of organizational success, particularly in the health care sector where the well-being of employees directly impacts patient care and outcomes.

Objective of the Study:

- To study the employee job satisfaction among one of the Kauvery Hospital, Chennai.
- To identify the factors influencing the job satisfaction.
- To determine the employee perception towards their job within the organization
- To understand the level of employee satisfaction and factors which make the employee desirable with respect to company policies, working conditions and other factor
- To analyze the relation between job satisfaction and the performance of Kauvery Hospital, Chennai.

Need of the Study:

The healthcare industry, crucial for public health and well-being, faces persistent challenges with employee job satisfaction. Stress, long hours, emotional labor, and bureaucratic pressures lead to job dissatisfaction, affecting performance and retention. This study investigates factors influencing job satisfaction among healthcare employees, including doctors, nurses, administrative staff, and support personnel. By identifying these factors, healthcare organizations can implement targeted strategies to enhance job satisfaction, leading to improved employee morale, reduced turnover, and better patient care. Addressing job satisfaction is critical for a stable and efficient workforce, and resilient healthcare systems that meet population needs

effectively. This study aims to provide valuable insights for policy-making and organizational practices, fostering a supportive and fulfilling work environment for all healthcare workers.

Scope of the Study:

The study aims to investigate employee job satisfaction concerning welfare measures at Kauvery Hospital, Chennai. Through a comprehensive review of existing literature, the study will establish a theoretical framework, highlighting the significance of employee welfare measures in healthcare settings and their impact on job satisfaction. The research objectives include assessing the current level of job satisfaction among Kauvery Hospital, Chennai employees, identifying existing welfare measures provided by the organization, and exploring employees' perceptions and satisfaction levels regarding these measures. The study's findings are expected to provide valuable insights for and similar healthcare organizations, offering recommendations for enhancing welfare measures to improve employee job satisfaction and organizational performance.

Hypothesis of the Study:

Hypothesis:

A hypothesis is an educated guess based on available evidence, serving as the starting point for any investigation. It transforms research questions into testable predictions, comprising essential components such as variables, population, and the relationships between variables. A research hypothesis, in particular, aims to examine the connection between two or more variables, providing a clear direction for the research study.

Null Hypothesis:

A hypothesis which assumes that there is no significant difference between sample statistics and population parameter is called null hypothesis. It is denoted by H_0 .

Alternate Hypothesis:

A hypothesis which assumes that there is significant difference between sample statistics and population parameter is called alternative hypothesis. It is denoted by H_1 .

Research Design:

A research design is a plan structure and strategy of investigation conceived. So as to answer research question and control variance. The research design adopted for the study is descriptive research design. It is the information needed to structure or solve the research problem.

Research Methodology:

Research is a careful investigation or inquiry epically through search for new factors in any branch of knowledge. Research methodology is the process of systematic investigation of any management problems and deals with research design data collection method. Sampling plan, sampling method.

Methods of Data Collection:

Data collection is a term used to describe process of preparing and collecting data. Systematic gathering of data for a particular purpose from various sources, that has been systematically observed, recorded, organized. Data are the basic inputs to any decision-making process in business. In this survey in order to meet the objectives of the study both primary data and secondary data were collected.

Primary Data:

The primary data are those which are collected for the first time and thus happen to be original characters in primary data do not already exist in any publications. In this study the primary data is collected by questionnaire. The questionnaire was handed over to various respondents and the data is collected.

Secondary Data:

The secondary data is the data that have been already collected by and readily available from other sources. Such data are cheaper and quickly obtained than the primary data. The secondary data are collected from the company records and magazines, journals, internet etc.,

Tool Used for Data Collection:

Among the various methods, which can be used to collect the primary data, the researcher has adopted questionnaire method. The researcher has prepared structured questionnaire, which contained predominately multiple-choice questions. The respondents opinion is gathered with regard to the problem with the help of the questionnaires.

Sampling Design:

A sample is a small representation of a larger whole. When some of the elements are selected with the intention of finding out something about the population from which they are taken, that group of elements is referred as a sample, and the process of selection is called sampling.

Sampling Unit:

The respondents of the study are part of population of employees of the Kauvery Hospital, Chennai. Each employee is considered to be sampling unit.

Population:

The number of employees in the Kauvery Hospital, Chennai is above 8000 employees.

Sample Size:

The number of item to be selected constitutes a sample. 110 employees are selected as sample for the research.

Sampling Criteria:

The sample was collected from all the level employees.

Frame Work for Analysis:

The primary data was from the respondents has been sorted, classified, edited and tabulated a proper format ad analysis by developing appropriate statistical tools. The researchers used SPSS software for recording and calculating 110 samples. The researcher used the following statistical tools to analyze the data procure from the respondents from area selected for the study.

Analytical Tools for the Study:

The tools used are

- Percentage analysis
- Chi-square
- Correlation

Percentage Analysis:

Percentage analysis is the method to represent raw streams of data as a percentage (a part in 100 percentages) for being understanding of collected data percentage analysis is applied to create contingency table form frequency distribution and represent the collected data for better understanding.

$$X. \text{ of respondent} = \text{Number of respondents in category} * 100 / \text{Total number of respondent}$$

Chi-Square:

A chi-square test is a statistical test used to compare observed results with expected results. The purpose of this test is to determine if a difference between observed data and expected data is due to chance, or if it is due to a relationship between the variables you are studying.

Correlation:

Correlation is simply defined as a relationship between the two variables. The purpose of using the correlation in research is to figure out which variables are connected.

Period of the Study:

The study was done in the period of 3 months from 25.03.2023 to 16.06.2023

Area of the Study:

This study is based on the analysis of job satisfaction among employees in the Kauvery Hospital, Chennai.

Limitations of the Study:

- This study is only limited to Kauvery Hospital, Chennai
- The study has been limited to the sample size of 110 respondents.
- The study was conducted in only one organization.

Company Profile:

Kauvery hospital launched its first hospital more than two decades ago, the founders of Kauvery Hospital have been determined on creating world class healthcare facilities that shall be affordable. The founding doctors set off on this dream in 1999 with a 30-bed hospital in Trichy, with single-minded focus on offering 'best-in-class healthcare, with a personal touch.' This was a very new concept in a tier 2 city like Trichy which lacked a tertiary care hospital at the time. Today, Kauvery is a multi-specialty hospital chain with 2250+ beds in six locations including Trichy, Chennai, Salem, Hosur, Tirunelveli and Bengaluru. With twelve hospitals and a workforce of over 8000+ Kauvery's mission is to provide exemplary secondary and tertiary care.

History of Kauvery Hospital:

Kauvery Hospital was founded in 1999 by Dr. S. Chandrakumar and Dr. S. Manivanna as a 30-bed facility in Tiruchirappalli. It was renamed in 2002 and expanded to include a cardiac center in 2004. The hospital acquired Seahorse Hospital in 2008 and opened a location in Chennai in 2011. Today, Kauvery Hospital is a multispecialty hospital chain with 5 locations in Tamil Nadu, including two in Chennai, offering a range of specialized services and treatments with a total capacity of over 1100 beds. The Alwarpet location is a 300-bed facility with centers of excellence in various specialties, easily accessible from all parts of Chennai.

Services:

Patient-Centric Medical Care:

In addition to the huge bed capacity, Kauvery Hospital Chennai places great emphasis on patient-centric care and ensures that all patients receive personalized attention and treatment. The hospital's comprehensive range of services includes preventive healthcare, diagnostic services, outpatient care, and inpatient treatment. Moreover, the hospital has a well-equipped emergency department that operates round the clock to cater to any medical emergencies that may arise.

Medical Research & Innovation

In addition to its exceptional medical services, Kauvery Hospital is dedicated to medical education and research. The hospital serves as a teaching institution and collaborates with renowned medical universities to impart knowledge and train the next generation of healthcare professionals. Through continuous research and innovation, Kauvery Hospital strives to stay at the forefront of medical advancements and provide cutting-edge treatments to its patients.

Specialties Offered at Kauvery Hospital, Chennai:

Spread across 2 campuses in Chennai, Kauvery Hospital has established itself as a center of medical excellence in various specialties. The hospital houses dedicated departments for cardiology, neurology, oncology, orthopedics, gastroenterology, and many more.

Cardiology:

Kauvery Hospital Chennai has a highly advanced cardiology department that offers comprehensive cardiac care. From preventive cardiology to advanced treatments for heart diseases, the hospital has a team of experienced cardiologists and cutting-edge facilities for accurate diagnosis and effective interventions.

Neurological Disorders:

Kauvery Hospital's neurology department specializes in the diagnosis and treatment of neurological disorders. This includes conditions such as stroke, epilepsy, Parkinson's disease, multiple sclerosis, migraine, neuropathy, and brain tumors. The hospital offers advanced neuroimaging techniques, neurosurgery, neurorehabilitation, and specialized treatments for neurological conditions.

Cancer:

Kauvery Hospital offers comprehensive treatments for various types of cancers, including breast cancer, lung cancer, gastrointestinal cancers, gynecological cancers, head and neck cancers, and blood-related cancers. The hospital's oncology services include chemotherapy, radiation therapy, targeted therapy, immunotherapy, and surgical interventions.

Gastrointestinal Disorders:

Kauvery Hospital Chennai has a specialized gastroenterology department that deals with diseases and disorders related to the digestive system. This includes conditions such as gastritis, peptic ulcers, gastro esophageal reflux disease (GERD), liver diseases, inflammatory bowel diseases (IBD), pancreatic disorders, and gastrointestinal cancers.

Orthopedic Conditions:

Kauvery Hospital's orthopedics department offers comprehensive care for various musculoskeletal conditions. This includes fractures, sports injuries, arthritis, degenerative joint diseases, spinal disorders, and congenital deformities. The hospital provides non-surgical treatments, minimally invasive surgeries, joint replacements, spinal surgeries, and orthopedic rehabilitation programs.

Trade name:	Kauvery Hospital
Company type:	Public
Traded as:	BSE: 524520
Industry:	Healthcare
Founded:	1999
Areas served:	Chennai, Trichy, Hosur, Salem, Bengaluru, Tirunelveli
Key people:	S Chandrakumar (Founder, Executive Chairman) Manivannan S Founder, Managing Director)
Services:	Hospitals
Number of employees:	8000+ (December, 2024)
Website:	www.kauveryhospital.com

Values:

- C - Continual Improvement
- H - Heartfelt Personal Touch
- E - Ethical
- E - Empathetic Care
- R - Real Accountability
- S - Service Excellence

Vision:

To be the most respected and trusted healthcare provider

Mission:

To make great healthcare affordable

Values:

- Continual Improvement
- Heartfelt Personal Touch
- Ethical
- Empathetic Care
- Real Accountability
- Service Excellence

Quality Policy:

- Kauvery Hospital & Research Center is committed to achieve customer satisfaction by excelling in service & patient care
- Kauvery Hospital & Research Center is also committed to practice safe & ethical medicine by deploying best of technology

Awards:

- ABK AOTS Convention – Rhodium Award
- Advanced Cardiac Care by Times of India Awards
- AHPI Awards 2024
- Best CSR Award by ASSOCHAM Tamil Nadu
- Best heart and lung transplant team

Clinical Performance:

- 2000+ Neuro Procedures
- 2500+ Cancer Procedures
- 2000+ Gastro Procedures
- 2000+ Joint Replacements
- 500+ Kidney Transplants & Procedures
- 60000+ Dialysis | Kidney Procedures
- 11000+ Heart Surgeries
- 10000+ Coronary Angiograms
- 2500+ Coronary Angioplasty
- 5000+ Open Heart Procedures
- Approved Centres for Heart & Lung Transplants

Services / Facilities Offered:

- Patient care. All categories of beds ranging from general ward to super deluxe (suites) are available.
- Emergency care. Equipped emergency/trauma care is available with well-trained doctors and support staff.
- International services. Catering to a good number of overseas patients. Corporate services. Empaneled to provide healthcare to the employees of large corporate.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Job Secure:

No Strong Spirit of Teamwork and Cooperation among Employees:

Quality is a Top Priority at the Hospital:

Correlation:

Satisfied With Work and Physical Working Conditions:

		Satisfied With Work	Physical Working Condition
Satisfied With Work	Pearson Correlation	1	.712**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0
	N	110	110

Physical Working Condition	Pearson Correlation	.712**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	
	N	110	110

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Satisfied With Work and Physical Working Conditions:

		Satisfied With Work	Job Secure
Satisfied With Work	Pearson Correlation	1	.869**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0
	N	110	110
Job Secure	Pearson Correlation	.869**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	
	N	110	110

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Chi-Square:

Adequate Planning of Hospital Objective:

	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Strongly Agree	40	36.7	3.3
Agree	56	36.7	19.3
Neutral	14	36.7	-22.7
Total	110		

Contribute to the Facility:

	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Strongly Agree	41	36.7	4.3
Agree	58	36.7	21.3
Neutral	11	36.7	-25.7
Total	110		

Test Statistics:

	Adequate Planning of Hospital Objective	Contribute to the Facility
Chi-Square	24.509a	30.891a
df	2	2
Asymp. Sig.	0	0

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 36.7.

Suggestions:

- Management can initiate remedial measures to improve general working conditions there by employees will be satisfied in their job.
- Proper guidance and counselling can be provided to employees so that their mental satisfaction will be improved.
- Organization can improve promotional facilities to the employees so that they will be motivated in their job.
- They can offer an better opportunities to employee's for their personal development.
- Providing health insurance and life insurance to the employee will helpful for their job satisfaction.
- They should also concentrate on training programs such as achieving self-development, increasing organization stability, helping to handle stress and tension
- Management should provide an opportunity to practice the learned in the workplace
- To get better response from employees the management should mostly concentrate on promotional aspects based on merit and seniority.
- Employee satisfaction index should be calculated periodically in order to spot any early sign of dip in the satisfaction levels of the employees

Conclusions:

The job satisfaction of health workers is an essential part of ensuring high quality care, dissatisfied health worker not only give poor quality, less efficient care there also evidence that affect patient satisfaction. Given the important role that health workers play in determining the effectiveness, efficiency and sustainability of health care system, it is imperative to understand what motivates them and the extent to which contextual variables in order to make them satisfy with job.

Job satisfaction is a positive approach about one's job resulting from an evaluation of its characteristics. Job satisfaction represents an attitude rather than behaviour. They believe that satisfied employees are more productive than dissatisfied has been a basic tenet. A person with a high level of job satisfaction holds positive feeling about the job. They also want a constant feeling of wellbeing, demand better work and family life balance, and look to the organization for fulfilling even their community needs.

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